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Automated Malaria Detection System Using Raspberry Pi and Ai-Based Image Processing

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ABSTRACT

Malaria remains one of the most serious infectious diseases, especially in tropical and developing regions where access to advanced healthcare facilities is limited. Early and accurate diagnosis is essential to prevent complications and reduce mortality. Traditional diagnostic methods rely on manual microscopic examination of blood smears, which is time-consuming, requires skilled personnel, and is prone to human error.

This project presents an automated malaria detection system using Raspberry Pi and artificial intelligence-based image processing techniques. The system utilizes a pre-trained Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model to analyze blood smear images and classify them as infected or uninfected. A Flask-based web interface is developed to allow users to upload images easily through a local network. Once the image is submitted, it is processed using OpenCV for preprocessing, followed by classification using the trained AI model. The Raspberry Pi acts as the central processing unit, handling image processing, model inference, and hardware control. Based on the result, a red LED indicates malaria-positive samples, while a green LED indicates healthy samples. The system operates offline, making it suitable for rural and resource-limited environments. This solution is cost-effective, portable, and user-friendly, enabling rapid and reliable malaria diagnosis. It reduces dependency on skilled technicians and supports early detection, contributing to improved healthcare accessibility and disease management.

Keywords: Malaria Detection, Raspberry Pi, Artificial Intelligence, Image Processing, Convolutional Neural Network, Blood Smear Analysis, OpenCV, Flask Web Interface, Embedded System, Healthcare Automation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Malaria is a serious mosquito-borne disease caused by Plasmodium parasites and continues to remain a major health concern in many developing and tropical countries [1]. Early and accurate diagnosis is essential because delayed detection can lead to severe complications and even death [2]. In most healthcare centers, malaria is commonly diagnosed by examining blood smear samples under a microscope, but this method is time-consuming, requires trained laboratory personnel, and is often affected by human error [3][4].

With the advancement of artificial intelligence and embedded systems, automated disease detection has become more practical and reliable [5]. Image processing and deep learning techniques, especially Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), have shown strong performance in identifying infected blood cells from microscopic images [6][7]. At the same time, low-cost computing devices such as Raspberry Pi make it possible to deploy such intelligent systems in rural and resource-limited areas [8].

This project proposes an Automated Malaria Detection System using Raspberry Pi and AI-Based Image Processing, where blood smear images are analyzed automatically using a trained AI model [9]. The system is designed to provide quick, affordable, and user-friendly diagnosis through a local web interface and LED-based indication, making it suitable for small clinics, mobile health units, and remote medical centers [10].

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Malaria diagnosis in many healthcare centers still depends on manual microscopic examination of blood smear samples, which requires skilled technicians, laboratory equipment, and considerable time. This traditional method is often slow, costly, and prone to human

error, especially in rural and resource-limited areas where medical facilities are limited. As a result, delayed or inaccurate diagnosis can affect timely treatment and increase health risks. Therefore, there is a need for an automated, low-cost, and reliable malaria detection system that can quickly analyze blood sample images and provide accurate results with minimal human intervention.

III. OBJECTIVES

- To develop an automated system for malaria detection using image processing and artificial intelligence.
- To implement a trained CNN model for classifying blood smear images as infected or uninfected.
- To integrate the AI model with Raspberry Pi for real-time and portable diagnosis.
- To design a simple Flask-based web interface for easy image upload and result display.
- To provide quick visual output using LED indicators for malaria-positive and healthy samples.

IV. LITERATURE SURVEY

1. Shilpi Saxena et al. (2023), in the paper “Developing an Artificial Intelligence for Screening Malaria Parasite from Peripheral Blood Smears,” proposed an AI-based screening method for detecting malaria parasites from microscopic blood smear images. The study focused on reducing the burden of manual diagnosis by using deep learning techniques. The system was trained to identify infected cells with improved sensitivity and faster screening time. The authors concluded that AI can support laboratory professionals by improving the speed and consistency of malaria diagnosis.

2. Tamal Kumar Kundu et al. (2023), in the paper “Utilizing Image Analysis with Machine Learning and Deep Learning to Identify Malaria Parasites in Conventional

Microscopic Blood Smear Images,” presented a malaria detection approach based on image analysis and machine learning models. The work combined image preprocessing, segmentation, and classification techniques to identify infected blood cells. The proposed method improved the accuracy of malaria detection and highlighted the importance of image quality and feature extraction in medical image diagnosis.

3. Shankar Shambhu et al. (2023), in the paper “Deep Learning-Based Computer Assisted Detection Techniques for Malaria Parasite Using Blood Smear Images,” introduced a computer-assisted detection system using deep learning algorithms for identifying malaria parasites. The study emphasized the use of convolutional neural networks for analyzing blood smear images efficiently. The proposed model reduced human effort in diagnosis and showed that automated systems can be useful in low-resource medical environments.

4. K. Hemachandran et al. (2023), in the paper “Performance Analysis of Deep Learning Algorithms in Malaria Detection,” carried out a comparative study of different deep learning models used for malaria diagnosis. The paper

analyzed the performance of multiple algorithms based on accuracy, precision, and processing speed. The study concluded that lightweight deep learning models are more suitable for deployment on compact systems like Raspberry Pi, where both speed and efficiency are important.

5. Sanya Sinha et al. (2023), in the paper “Computer-Aided Diagnosis of Malaria through Transfer Learning using the ResNet50 Backbone,” proposed a transfer learning-based malaria classification system using microscopic blood cell images.

6. A. Murmu et al. (2024), in the paper “DLRFNet: Deep Learning with Random Forest Network for Malaria Parasite Classification,” proposed a hybrid classification approach that combines deep learning with machine learning techniques for malaria detection. The system extracted image features using a CNN and used a Random Forest classifier for final decision-making. The proposed method improved classification robustness and showed good performance even in noisy or low-quality image conditions, making it practical for real-world medical applications.

Comparison Table

Author & Year	Technology Used	Key Feature	Limitation
Shilpi Saxena et al. (2023)	CNN, AI	Fast parasite detection	Needs large dataset
Tamal Kundu et al. (2023)	ML & Image Processing	Improved accuracy	Complex preprocessing
Shankar Shambhu et al. (2023)	Deep Learning (CNN)	Reduced manual effort	High computation
K. Hemachandran et al. (2023)	DL Models Comparison	Performance analysis	Limited real-time use
Sanya Sinha et al. (2023)	Transfer Learning (ResNet)	High accuracy	Requires tuning
A. Murmu et al. (2024)	CNN + Random Forest	Robust classification	Slightly complex model

V. WORKING OF SYSTEM

Fig 1: Design of the system

1. Blood Smear Image Input:

The system starts by taking a blood sample image, either captured using a microscope camera or uploaded through the web interface.

2. Raspberry Pi:

It acts as the main controller, managing image processing, running the AI model, and controlling the output devices.

3. Image Processing:

The input image is preprocessed using OpenCV, where it is resized and cleaned to improve accuracy.

4. AI Model (CNN):

The processed image is analyzed using a trained Convolutional Neural Network, which classifies the sample as infected or uninfected.

5. Decision Unit:

Based on the model output, the system decides the final result.

6. Output (LED & Web Interface):

- Red LED → Malaria detected
- Green LED → Healthy sample
- Web interface → Displays result to the user

VI. SYSTEM DESIGN

1. Overview of System

The proposed Automated Malaria Detection System using Raspberry Pi and AI-Based Image Processing is designed to

detect malaria infection from microscopic blood smear images automatically. The system combines image acquisition, image preprocessing, deep learning-based classification, and result indication into a compact and portable setup. It uses a Raspberry Pi as the main controller, a camera/web interface for image input, an AI model for classification, and LED indicators along with a web page for output display.

The main purpose of the system is to reduce the time, effort, and dependency on manual microscopic diagnosis. Once a blood smear image is provided to the system, it is processed and analyzed to determine whether the sample is infected or uninfected. Based on the result, the system gives both visual output and digital output, making it suitable for use in rural clinics, diagnostic labs, and portable healthcare units.

2. Components with Description

2.1. Blood Smear Image Input

The blood smear image input is the first stage of the system. It provides the microscopic image of the blood sample for malaria detection. The image can be captured using a USB camera, digital microscope, or uploaded through the web interface. This image serves as the primary data source for further processing and analysis.

2.2. Raspberry Pi

Fig.2.:Raspberry Pi

The Raspberry Pi acts as the central processing unit of the system. It controls all operations such as receiving the image, preprocessing it, running the AI model, and generating the final result. It also

manages the Flask web server and controls the LED indicators through its GPIO pins. Due to its compact size and low power consumption, it is ideal for portable healthcare applications.

3. USB Camera / Microscope Camera

Fig.3. USB Camera

The USB camera is used to capture clear and detailed images of blood smear slides. It connects directly to the Raspberry Pi and allows the system to collect microscopic images in digital form. Good image quality is important because the accuracy of malaria detection depends heavily on the clarity of the blood cell image.

4. Image Processing Unit (OpenCV)

The image processing unit uses OpenCV to prepare the captured blood smear image before it is analyzed by the AI model. This stage includes operations such as resizing, noise removal, brightness adjustment, and normalization. These steps improve image quality and help the model make more accurate predictions.

5. AI Model (Convolutional Neural Network - CNN)

The CNN model is the main intelligent component of the system. It is trained

using blood smear images to recognize the difference between infected and uninfected cells. After receiving the processed image, the model performs classification and predicts whether malaria parasites are present in the sample or not.

6. Flask Web Interface

The Flask web interface provides a simple and user-friendly platform for interacting with the system. It allows the user to upload a blood smear image through a browser and view the prediction result instantly. This makes the system easy to operate even for users with limited technical knowledge.

7. Decision Unit

The decision unit receives the prediction result from the AI model and decides the final output of the system. If the image is classified as infected, the system marks it as malaria-positive. If the image is

classified as uninfected, the system marks it as healthy. This unit ensures the correct

output is passed to both the web interface and the LED indicators.

7. LED Indicators

The system uses two LEDs for quick visual indication of the result:

- **Red LED** → Malaria detected
- **Green LED** → Healthy sample

These LEDs are connected to the Raspberry Pi GPIO pins and help users understand the diagnosis instantly without needing to read the web page.

9. Power Supply

Fig.4. Power Supply

The entire system is powered using a 5V DC power adapter or a portable power bank. It provides the necessary electrical power to the Raspberry Pi, camera, and LED indicators. This makes the system portable and suitable for field-level deployment.

VII. RESULTS

The Automated Malaria Detection System using Raspberry Pi and AI-Based Image Processing was successfully developed and tested for identifying malaria infection from blood smear images. The system was able to capture or receive blood sample

images, preprocess them using image processing techniques, and classify them accurately with the help of the trained CNN model. During testing, the model successfully distinguished between infected and uninfected samples and displayed the result through both the web interface and LED indicators. The red LED glowed when malaria was detected, while the green LED indicated a healthy sample, making the output simple and easy to understand.

The Raspberry Pi efficiently handled the complete operation of the system,

including image input, preprocessing, prediction, and output generation. The Flask-based web interface worked smoothly and allowed users to upload images and receive instant results in a user-friendly manner. The overall system demonstrated that AI-based malaria detection can be implemented effectively on a low-cost embedded platform without requiring internet access. The results show that the proposed system is reliable, portable, and suitable for use in rural healthcare centers, small laboratories, and mobile diagnostic units where quick and affordable malaria screening is needed.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The Automated Malaria Detection System using Raspberry Pi and AI-Based Image Processing provides an effective and practical solution for the early diagnosis of malaria. The project successfully combines image processing, artificial intelligence, and embedded system technology to create a low-cost and portable diagnostic tool. By analyzing blood smear images automatically, the system reduces the dependency on manual microscopic examination and helps in obtaining faster and more consistent results.

The use of Raspberry Pi as the central processing unit makes the system compact, energy-efficient, and suitable for deployment in remote and resource-limited areas. The integration of a CNN-based AI model improves the reliability of classification, while the web interface and LED indicators make the system simple and user-friendly. Overall, the proposed system demonstrates that modern AI-based healthcare solutions can play an important role in improving disease detection, supporting medical staff, and enhancing healthcare accessibility in rural and underdeveloped regions.

IX. FUTURE SCOPE

The future scope of this project is wide, as the system can be further improved and

expanded for advanced medical applications. In the future, the model can be trained with a larger and more diverse dataset to improve detection accuracy and make it more robust under different image conditions. The system can also be enhanced to identify different species of malaria parasites, which would make it more useful for detailed diagnosis and treatment planning.

Another possible improvement is the addition of parasite counting functionality, which can help estimate the severity of infection. The project can also be integrated with cloud storage, allowing patient reports and diagnosis history to be stored and accessed remotely. A mobile application can be developed to make the system more accessible and user-friendly for healthcare workers in the field. In addition, the same platform can be extended to detect other blood-related diseases using microscopic image analysis. With further development, this system can become a more powerful and intelligent diagnostic tool for real-world healthcare use.

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